

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17097273

Devastating Effect Of Insurgency In Economic Development Of Katsina State Nigeria

Ahmad Garba Basakkwace; Samaila Mukhtar; Abdullahi Mode; Isah Shehu Shagari & Bashar Ahmad

Umaru Ali Shinkafi Polytechnic Sokoto. Nigeria

ABSTRACT

Katsina state has faced a severe security crisis, marked by widespread insurgencies banditry, cattle rustling, kidnapping and communal conflicts which have displaced several communities and disrupted economic activities. The state's economy was floundering under the weight of security situation was dire. With banditry and violence threatening the lives and livelihoods of the people. It is argued that banditry is responsible for the deplorable state of socio-economic indices in the region. Specifically, it was alleged that bandit activities such as kidnapping for ransom, cattle rustling, daily attacks on villages have a devastating impact on the average per capita income of the people, and food security, among others. The governor of the state last year established well trained and equipped local community watch corps. Operating in vulnerable areas such as Malumfashi, Dandume, Faskari, and Musawa, these Corps played a pivotal role in reducing insurgencies in the state. Therefore, the paper concludes that banditry and insurgencies largely has negative impact on economic development in Katsina state. The study recommends that the Katsina state government should provide enabling environment by adequately and regularly empowering the local security outfits with modern sophisticated weapons to face the bandits squarely. Additionally, Government should come out with policies and programmes that involve necessary equipment and materials for the people to alleviate poverty and unemployment through the cultivation of entrepreneurial spirit and acquisition of relevant skills that will promote them economic development, enhanced income generation and economic independence.

Keywords: Banditry, Insurgencies, Economic Development, Security.

INTRODUCTION

Katsina state is located in the Sahel Savanna region of Northern Nigeria between latitudes 11°07'49N-13°22'57 North and longitude 6°52'03E-9°02'40 East. Its principal neighbours are Zamfara and Sokoto states to the west, Jigawa and Kano to the east, Maradi and Damagaram in Niger Republic to the East and North East and Kaduna State to the South. Katsina State was created out of the former Kaduna State on Wednesday, September 23, 1987, by the federal military administration of General Badamasi Babangida. The State has a population of 5.79 million people according to the 2006 provisional census figures. The main occupations of the people are farming, traditional handcrafts and animal husbandry. Maize, millet, guinea corn, cassava, beans are the major food crops, while cotton, tobacco, sugarcane, soya beans and groundnuts are the major cash crops. The state is also one of the major producers of tomatoes, pepper and onion in the country. A part from crop farming, the state is one of the major producers of livestock such as cows, sheep, goats, and camels. On 17th of June 2024, the Northwest Governor's Forum in collaboration with the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), has met and discussed pressing security challenges facing the area in Katsina State capital. In recent years Northwest states including Katsina has been marked in the increase in incidents of banditry, terrorism, and communal conflicts.

These issues have had devastating consequences for the local population, resulting in significant loss of lives, severe disruption to livelihoods and widespread destruction of properties. H.E. Dikko Radda, Governor of Katsina State emphasizes the critical nature of the summit: ‘‘This gathering marks a turning point in our fight against insecurity. The challenges we face demand immediate and collective action. By uniting our efforts and resources, we can forge a path towards lasting peace and prosperity for our people. The time to act is now, and together, we will reclaim the safety and stability that our region deserves’’ he said.

Security, stability, peaceful co-existence and good governance are prerequisites for the achievement of any meaningful economic development of any given country. It has been established that there is a strong connection between adequate security and development generally (Mungadi et al, 2020). However, for some time now, security challenges have continued to remain a major setback to achieving meaningful development in most north western state particularly in Katsina State. Insecurity does not only pose threats to the lives and property of the people, it also discourages local businesses, scares away farmers from their farms and foreign investment and portends a bad image for the state (Ekene, 2015). Security challenges posed by these insurgents’ activities have become a serious concern that needs to be tackled as a matter of seriousness and urgency to create an enabling environment for development that aimed at improving the livelihood of people of Katsina State. However, despite Katsina State government efforts to bring to an end the menace of banditry and insurgent activities spending billions of Naira on security over the past years, the security situation remains major challenge to development (Olufemi, 2015). Banditry is a form of crime that can pose a serious threat to communities in the affected areas. The criminal activities associated with banditry include various acts of violence and theft that cause physical and economic harm to local residents. The fact that many bandits are well known by the local community creates complexity in addressing this issue, as it can cause fear and mistrust within the community. Efforts to tackle bandits’ banditry behaviours should include a holistic approach and involve collaboration between authorities, traditional rulers and community’s leaders to identify and address the root causes of banditry activities (Muhammad I (2020). Note that Agriculture is both the major source of income and economic development in households in almost all the local government areas of Katsina State, but detrimentally, the activities of bandits have seriously crippled farming activities in those affected areas. The main source of economic development as earlier noted is Agriculture. Amazingly, accusing fingers are repeatedly being pointed at the military and other sister agencies for lack of diligence and thorough investigation, conspiracy to cover up suspects and indiscriminate and rampant release of suspects (Ibrahim T (2020). It is an irony, that although, security personnel have said to be deployed to the state, the security situation in the State has continued to worsen and became more complicated by the day. Traditional rulers at different levels had complained bitterly about the unbecoming attitude of some security agents claiming that whenever they were directed to the point of potential attack by bandits, they deliberately divert their attention or stall action to a different direction citing lack of order from the above. This unpatriotic and unprofessional behaviour has complicated and worsened the security situation.

Areas Worst Hit by the Insurgency

On 6th of September 2025, at least seven people were reportedly killed when some suspected bandits armed with sophisticated weapon attacked Magajin Wando village in the Dandume Local Government area of Katsina State. The following local government areas are considered to be frontline zones of violent banditry and kidnappings. These included Jibiya, Funtua, Sabuwa, Danmusa, Kankiya, Danja, Bakori, Charanchi, Dutinma, Matazu, Malumfashi and Batagarawa. Recently 32 worshippers were shot dead by the bandits inside mosque. The mosque, located in the village of Unguwan Mantau in Malumfashi local government. In January this year, at least 21 people have been killed in an ambush by bandits in the village of Baure, in the Safana local government.in June 2025; bandits have killed at least 24 farmers, and 3 other residents in Kankara local government area. In July this year also there’s a night of deadly bandits’ attack which claimed 19 persons at Gobirawa community in Kuki ward of Dutsinma local government area. Also 6 people have been killed and two others abducted after bandits attacked in

the Bakori local government. There is no doubt that in most if not all the local government and communities in Katsina State are still under the constant attacks and harassment by the bandits.

A Resolute Stance on the Security in the State

Provision of security has been identified as one of the foremost cardinal priority of the present administration in the state. The pervasive banditry and cattle rustling had displaced entire communities in the state, leaving residents in constant fear. Understanding hinges on safety, the state government adopted a multifaceted approach to reduce the crime and restore public trust by actively involving local residents in their own protection. Recognising that the number of security agencies is not sufficient to cover the entire state, the government identified a need to involve local communities directly in security efforts. The corps' primary role is to act as a supplementary security force, working in collaboration with traditional and conventional security agencies to enhance security of lives and properties of the people in the state. In an effort to tackle insecurity in the state, the government includes dialogue with the bandits, establishing surveillance centres and providing rapid response.

Major Causes of Insurgency in Katsina State

- Unemployment

The increasing rate of youth's unemployment is what prompts the jobless youths to resort to violent acts of criminal activities including banditry.

- Poverty

Poverty is identified as among the major reason youths resort into crime. Million lack access to basic education, clean water, food and basic health. Poverty alleviation programs maybe a potential solution.

- Proliferation of Arms

The inflows of fire arms across the Jibia border and other Nigerian borders prompts insecurity, proper surveillance is needed to mitigate such risks. Proliferation of weapons and arms are veritable factors responsible for banditry and other security challenges in the State.

- Lack of Access to Basic Amenities

Poor governance is partly responsible for the emergence of insurgency, kidnapping for ransom and arm banditry.

- Corruption at all Level

Corruption is one of the most significant factors contributing to security challenges.

- Injustice

Condoning and prevalent of injustice meted to the Fulani's by the traditional leaders within their domain when the Fulani headers encroaches into the farms of their people, injustice meted by the police when arrested, and injustice to Fulani when taking to courts for prosecution.

- Weak security System

Weak security system complements the alarming rate of banditry in Katsina State. Armed banditry, kidnapping for ransom, rustling of cows thrive in the areas because of the absence of government, especially security agents and other social infrastructure which disconnected the villages from urban centres.

Effects of Banditry on Economic Development in Katsina State

The issue of kidnapping for ransom, cattle rustling and killings of individuals have become daily affairs in various towns and villages of Katsina state. Bandits are known to operate many camps from which they have consistently launch deadly attacks on many villages in Katsina State. The high wire banditry raging in many neighbouring northern states has now spilled into several villages and towns in some local government areas in the State, and consequently putting the security of the entire state in jeopardy. Bloodletting bandits are occupying strategic parts of the state and other local governments Areas where they continue to wreak unprecedented havoc on communities in these areas. The prevalent insecurity in Katsina state has cost the state enormous resources. Government has consistently supported security

agents with vehicles, motor cycles and other security gadgets in order for them to carry out their operation without hitches. This is because government has noted that security plays a vital role in the sustenance and existence of human populace. When people's security is assured, it gives people and government the confidence and determination to get on with the business of building their lives to be self-reliant and self-sufficient. People cannot go to farm or partake in any economic activities if their lives are exposed to insecurity, molestation and violent killings. No society can thrive in an atmosphere of insecurity. According to Abdulrahman (2020), the effects of insecurity include unwanted displacement; fear of unknown attacks and deprivation of basic needs such as access to quality education, good drinking-water, decent food and access to health care services. All these could only be gotten through peace. For instance, displaced persons are subject to a variety of health hazards and are prone to a high mortality rate. This is largely because they don't have access to good food, clean water, and clean sanitation. No doubt the people of Kankara, Dandume, Faskari, Musawa and some other parts of Katsina state are in serious economic problems this is as a result of constant attacks killings and plunders by the bandits. The poverty rate has triple with many people going to bed hungry. Almost all the economic activities in the area have come to standstill. And many people died including children and elderly as the result of lack of medicated attention. Security without doubt is necessary for the survival of a nation, and the human population, and economic diversification. The productive sector of the economy which depends largely on the availability and regular supply of raw materials is suffering from the prevalent insecurity cutting off going to markets on market days and the supply of markets goods.

The bandits are moved by quest for economic accumulation while the victims are individuals and communities with material valuables. The most common examples of banditry in Nigeria are armed robbery, kidnapping, cattle rustling, sexual violence and village raids (Chukwuma cited in Abubakar & Ibrahim (2020). There is a devastating effect of banditry on food security especially in Kastina state where farmers are kidnapped, taken to the forest and huge amount of money paid before they are released. This dreadful condition impoverishes farmers by forcing them to sell their assets, including their fields, in order to obtain money for ransom (Muhammad I 2020). According to Ibrahim (2020), one of the kidnapping cases occurred on the 4th of October, 2020, in Mallamawa Village, Jibia local government area, where 22 farmers working on farmlands were kidnapped, with some escaping. On the 3rd of May, 2020, bandits chased off some farmers who were on their farmlands in the Faskari local government area of the State, preparing for the farming season. "Who told you guys there would be farming this season?" the bandits questioned rhetorically. The alarming event instilled panic among the farmers, deterring them from continuing with the season's farming preparations. Some farmers and pastoralists have abandoned farming and cattle grazing and taken refuge in neighbouring states or camps for internally displaced persons with very poor living conditions. This has negative impact on average per-capita of people and food security given that Nigeria is already one of the countries with highest number of hungry citizens, with millions especially in northern Nigeria who are at risk of dying from famine. As a result, some farmers in the state have warned that if the government does not effectively address the revival of banditry, the state could face a historic food catastrophe (Sardauna, 2020). Education, which is one of the key drivers of socio-economic development, has also been negatively impacted by bandit operations. There was also an abduction of 333 boys from Government Science Secondary School in Katsina state in December 2020. Banditry activities have led to the closure of several schools, which is not good for education in the state, coupled with the fact that the North West is the richest geopolitical zone in Nigeria, with a literacy rate of 29.7% and the highest number of out-of-school children in Nigeria (Ejiofor, 2022).

Major Findings on Insurgencies in Katsina State

The major finding by this paper is that insurgency negatively impacts economic development by destroying resources, destroying infrastructures, displacing people in IDP camps, and lastly it hinder growth and worsening hunger and poverty. Findings from the paper revealed that banditry was found to have had a significant impact on economic development in Katsina state. It showed that a percentage

increase in banditry, on the average affect development in Katsina State. The findings are in agreement with Ajibola (2021).

It was discovered from the analysis that impact of banditry activities has negative relationship with socioeconomic development of Katsina state. Impact of banditry has statistically significantly determinant of economic development in Katsina state. The analysis revealed that a percentage change in the impact of banditry activities, on the average affect economic development in Katsina state.

CONCLUSION

From the content of this paper the effects of insurgency on economic development in Katsina state, series of attack, impact of banditry, and mechanism for addressing banditry, has greater effects on economic development of Katsina state. The paper concludes that bandits and banditry activities in Katsina state has played a vigorous role in the determinants of economic development. Again, the bandit has contributed to the difficulty of education and healthcare accessibility, closed of businesses whenever there is bandit attack and increase in cost of general goods and services especially farm products due to bandit attacks on farmland which mitigates the financial burden associated with economic development thereby promoting the high-cost security provisioning in Katsina state. It is argued that banditry is responsible for the deplorable state of socio-economic indices in the State. Specifically, it was alleged that bandit activities such as kidnapping for ransom, cattle rustling, and daily village attacks have a devastating impact on the average per capita income of the people, and food security, among others.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The wheel of development of any country lies on the shoulders of how secure, productive and creative are the people especially the youths and young graduates. The government, parents and guardians have obligations to ensure that our society is free from any security threats and at the same time, people are empowered to discharge their obligations to the society and to better their life. In the light of the issues discussed above, the following recommendations are proffered:

- ❖ The Katsina State government should provide enabling environment by empowering the local security outfits with all the necessary modern equipment and gadgets. Government should curtail joblessness and criminal activities through the creation of entrepreneurial and skill acquisition programmes to engage the youth and make them earn income and become economically independent.
- ❖ There should be adequate installation of modern technology as well as proper surveillance to check-mate infiltration of people from other countries to avoid trans-border crimes, which are part of the igniting factors heightening banditry in Nigeria.
- ❖ In finding lasting solution to insurgency, local government and traditional rulers, stakeholders should be actively and fully involved in any measure adopted against bandits and banditry activities in the state.
- ❖ Katsina state should adopt amnesty program of disarmament, reintegration and rehabilitation of repentant insurgents.

REFERENCES

- Abdulrahman, A. (2020) 'Armed Banditry and Human Security in North Western Nigeria: The Impacts and the Way Forward', *Journal of Humanities Social and Management Sciences*, 1(1), 89–107.
- Abubakar, L.U. & Ibrahim, M.S. (2020). Al-ghazzali's theory of virtue: An agent for addressing rural banditry and conflict in North-west Nigeria. *Journal of Applied Philosophy*, 8 (18):1597-0779.
- Ajibola O, O. (2021). Terrorism and Insurgency in Northern Nigeria: A study of the Origins and Nature of Boko Haram; *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*. 2015; 5(12):6-15.
- Ejiofor, P.F. (2022). Beyond ungoverned spaces: Connecting the dots between relative deprivation, banditry, and violence in Nigeria. *African Security*, 15(2), 111-141.

- Ibrahim, T. (2020). Nigeria: Bandits abduct 22 farmers in Katsina. Retrieved from allafrica.com/stories/2020/100606.32.
- Muahmmed, I. (2020). Ripped by militia attacks, Shiroro communities lose farming season, likely facing future famine. HumAngle News. Retrieved from: <https://humangle.ng/ripped-by-militiaattacks-shiroro-communities-lose-farming-season-likely-facing-future-famine>.
- Mungadi .D. D., Yusuf, S., Jeremiah .S. O., Owa .F. T., Abubakar .I. A., Agbo-Madaki .A. A., Oyinloye .G. O. & Onibiyo .E. R. (2020). Roadmap to Tackling Insurgency, Armed Banditry and Kidnapping in the North West Region of Nigeria. Journal of Xidian University Vol. 14, Issue 10, ISSN No:1001-2400 [https://doi.org/10.37896/jxu14.10/095927JP\(925\)](https://doi.org/10.37896/jxu14.10/095927JP(925)).
- Olufemi J. (2015). Nigerian Spends ₦4.62 trillion on National Security in 5 Years, Yet widespread insecurity remains. Premium Times, 2015. Retrieved from <http://www.premiumtimesng.com>
- Sardauna, F. (2020). Food crisis looms as banditry resurfaces in Katsina. Retrieved from: <https://www.thisdaylive.com/index.php/2020/05/09/food-crisis-looms>